

Regional employment and response to labour market shocks

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Abstract

Labour market shocks differ across countries and regions. One way the economy can adjust for adverse regional shocks to employment is by labour mobility. In this paper, we study the population response to regional labour market shocks via migration. We draw on the EU-LFS microdata in the EU-27 over the period 1995–2020 for the working-age population. The data allow us to perform our analyses for the detailed NUTS2 level, as well as consider commuting-zones. We adopt an IV approach with an industry shift-share instrument and account for (potential) time lag in the migratory process by including an error-correction term. We find that in 10 years population movement of potential workers generally corrects for about 50% of a shock to regional employment at the NUTS2 and commuting-zone level. This overall population elasticity, however, hides substantial differences in elasticities with women, individuals aged 25 to 44, foreign-born and higher educated individuals reporting higher population elasticities. In addition, our results are driven by Western European countries. The initial population response to employment shocks is insignificant in a sample of Eastern European countries. Also, the migratory response is found to be more delayed when a region is confronted with a negative shock to employment.

Keywords: employment, unemployment, labour market, shocks to employment, European Union, labour mobility, migration

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Regional employment and response to labour market shocks

1. Introduction¹

Regional disparities in income are large in EU-27. There was some regional convergence in the first decade after year 2000, but since the financial and debt crises, convergence at the EU level has largely come to a standstill (Monfort, 2020; Pina & Sicari, 2021). Moreover, in many EU member states, within country regional disparities measured by the coefficient of variation of GDP per capita at NUTS2 regional level have increased in the last two decades (Monfort, 2020).

One reason for these within-country disparities are differences in employment rates. These disparities at NUTS 2 level are displayed in Figure 1 for the EU-27 countries (with two or more NUTS2 regions), where Italy, Spain, Belgium, and Hungary report relatively high regional disparities. Also, while regional disparities in (un)employment in the EU seemed to diminish at the beginning of the 21st century, the cohesion in the labour market deteriorated after the economic and financial crisis (Diaconu, 2014; Martins Ferreira, 2008; Prado & Zdrentu, 2011). Furthermore, Landesmann and Römisch (2006) find that capital city regions and regions that are specialised in modern industries have relatively better employment prospects as compared to other regions.

Figure 1. Regional disparities in employment rates among 15 to 64 year olds in EU-27 at NUTS2 level

Note: Dispersion of regional employment rates (at NUTS2 level) is the coefficient of variation (CV) of regional employment rates in a country weighted by the absolute population of each region. Eurostat (2021b).

¹ We are grateful for many insightful comments from Robert Stehrer.

Also, labour market shocks (measured by changes in regional employment) due to the technological transformation and the transition to a low-carbon economy will differ across countries and regions. Some regions will experience increasing demand for labour, while other regions will suffer from a lack of demand. There is suggestive evidence that prospective labour demand shocks stemming from digitalisation and automation will impact less prosperous regions more. Looking at the risk of automation among regions, OECD finds a negative correlation between the percentage of jobs at risk of automation and the income per capita (OECD, 2019).² Hence, adverse labour market shocks may slow down or reverse convergence in the EU.

One way for the economy to adjust to negative regional labour market shocks is for workers to move to other regions where the number of jobs is increasing or is expected to increase. Studying to what extent and how fast the economy ‘self-corrects’ via (regional) migration in the face of (potential future) regional shocks is important to understand the potential and need for policy interventions to lessen the impact of such shocks. How much and how fast regions adjust to employment shocks through population movement is the key question in this study.

There is substantial literature dealing with labour mobility between EU countries and how much EU-wide internal mobility contributes to mitigating asymmetric economic shocks to member states (Arpaia et al., 2016; Basso et al., 2019; Beyer et al., 2015).³ This interest is primarily inspired by Mundell’s (1961) early work on optimal currency areas and builds on the seminal work of Blanchard and Katz (1992). The present study is related to this line of research in the sense that if labour mobility of workers across EU member states is large and responsive to labour market shocks to member states, it is likely that the regional response is also large. Also, substantial mobility at the regional level can co-exist with limited mobility response across countries.

Our work is most closely related to that of Amior and Manning (2018). In their pivotal work, the researchers study the persistence of regional unemployment across US commuting zones (CZs). Building on the work of Blanchard and Katz (1992), Amior and Manning (2018) derive an error-correction mechanism to account for (potential) time lag in the migratory process and the associ-

² OECD regional TL2 level which broadly corresponds to the NUTS2 classification.

³ We use the terms ‘mobility’ and ‘migration’ interchangeably to describe movement of people of working-age in and out of NUTS2 EU regions. In EU parlance, ‘mobility’ is used to describe movements of people within the EU and the word ‘migration’ to people moving between EU and non-EU countries. Our analysis focuses on to what extent people of working-age move in and out of regions and is not explicitly concerned about where people are coming from or going to.

ated labour market disequilibrium. Doing so, they find that population corrects for a substantial portion of the shock to local employment, but always lags behind employment (even after 20 years). Other contributions to the literature indicate substantial heterogeneities in the population elasticities to shock in employment depending on, among other, gender, age, country of birth and level of education (Basso et al., 2019; Bound & Holzer, 2000; Faggian et al., 2007; Huber, 2018; Macisco & Pryor, 1963; Topel, 1986).

In our study, we adopt the error-correction-model of Amior and Manning (2018) to the EU Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) microdata over the period 1995-2020 for the working-age population in the EU-27 at the detailed and barely studied NUTS2 level. An additional contribution is that we consider CZs stretching across one or more NUTS2 regions. Last, using EU-LFS microdata, we are able to identify heterogeneities in population elasticities to employment.

We find that in 10 years population on average corrects for about 50% of a shock to regional employment at the NUTS2 and CZ level in the EU-27, which is (as expected) generally lower than population elasticities in the US. The overall population elasticity to employment also hides substantial differences in elasticities with women, individuals aged 25 to 44, foreign-born and higher educated individuals reporting higher population elasticities. In addition, our results are driven by Western European countries and the migratory response is found to be more delayed when a region is confronted with a negative shock to employment.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data

To study the persistence of regional unemployment and identify the response to labour market shocks, we draw on Eurostat's annual EU Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) microdata.⁴ The EU-LFS is the largest cross-sectional European household sample survey which covers the labour participation (employed, unemployed and the population outside the labour force) of the population aged

⁴ We use the 2021 release, version 1, with data from 1983 up to 2020. In addition, we complement the microdata with Eurostat's LFS indicators (last update: April 28, 2022) for Austria, Germany, and the Netherlands due to missing or aggregated information on NUTS regions. These LFS indicators are based on the results of the EU-LFS (with some adjustments, corrections and reconciliation) (Eurostat, 2022b).

15 and over in 35 participating countries (Eurostat, 2022a).⁵ A major strength of this survey is its focus on comparability across countries and over time. To ensure this comparability the EU-LFS adopts the same concepts and definitions, uses common classifications, follows International Labour Organisation guidelines and records the same set of characteristics in each country (Eurostat, 2022a). Country specific annual sample sizes vary from just under 13,000 for Finland in 1995 to almost 455,000 for Italy in 2005.

We restrict our analyses to the EU-27 over the period 1995–2020.⁶ For our analyses, we aggregate the microdata at the country and regional level. In addition, while our main analyses focus on the working-age population (ages 15-64), we perform separate analyses for multiple demographic subgroups to assess the heterogeneity in responses. The working-age population is defined as the number of individuals aged 15-64 residing in a country or region and employment as the number of people in these populations doing paid work in the seven days prior to the survey. To guarantee representativeness, we rely on weighted counts for national and regional population and employment using the yearly weighting factor provided by Eurostat.

Given our aim to estimate how mobility absorbs labour market shocks over a larger period, the data pose three main challenges. First, to identify regional population responses to shocks in unemployment, we utilise the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) classification level 2.⁷ However, over the years studied the NUTS2 classifications were updated leading to boundary shifts and sometimes entirely new classifications within countries. To account for these changes and obtain consistent regions over time, we aggregated some of the regions keeping the classification as close as possible to NUTS2.⁸ In addition, (small) boundary shifts were ignored in view of keeping the dataset as large as possible.⁹

⁵ The participating countries are the EU Member States, the United Kingdom, three EFTA countries and four EU candidate countries, where each country is responsible for collecting the data. The data collection started in 1983, with data for individual countries generally available depending on each enlargement of the EU. More information on the EU-LFS is available at Eurostat (2022a).

⁶ For this period, detailed information is available on the NUTS2 regions as well as the NACE (industry) classification.

⁷ This (NUTS2) is a geographical classification subdividing the economic territory of the European Union (EU) and the UK into basic regions for the application of regional policies (Eurostat, 2022c). The NUTS classification level 1, which we also use, typically contains several NUTS2 areas and corresponds to the major socio-economic regions (Eurostat, 2022c).

⁸ An overview of these aggregations is available in the Appendix (Table A1).

⁹ Also, some boundary shifts did not have a statistical effect, as the area concerned was not covered before (e.g. France, Saint Barthélemy) (Eurostat, 2021a).

Second, our instrumental variable analysis builds on an instrument derived from (changes to) employment levels in different economic activities over the period 2005-2020. However, the statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community (NACE)¹⁰ had a major revision from NACE Rev. 1.1 (adopted in the EU-LFS from 1992-2007) to Rev. 2 (adopted from 2008 onwards). With this change, NACE classification increased from 17 sections (A-Q in Rev. 1.1) to 21 sections (A-U in Rev. 2) (Eurostat, 2008). A broad correspondence between the sections of both versions can be established (Eurostat, 2008). While some sections are easily comparable between both versions of the classification, this however is a rough one-to-one correspondence and not a complete one, as some new concepts at the section level were introduced with the NACE Rev. 2 classification.^{11,12} Third, countries joined the EU at different points in time, with data generally only being available from the year of their membership of (or a few years before) the EU and onwards. This means that we have an unbalanced panel. While this is not an issue for the econometric analysis, it does affect the interpretation of the estimates. We address this by looking at subsamples in the section on robustness.

2.2. Regions and commuting zones in Europe

As mentioned in the previous section, we utilise the NUTS classification level 2 with some aggregations to have consistent geographical regions. Only a few researchers have used such detailed region aggregations.¹³ We further add to the literature by estimating the link between regional employment and population at the level of CZs. The zones are generally used in population and economic analyses to identify areas which share a common (labour) market (Tolbert & Sizer, 1996).

Within Europe, CZs are typically defined as surrounding travel-to-work areas of a city where at least 15% of the population commutes to the city for work (Eurostat, 2019).¹⁴ In the EU-LFS microdata, however, no such detailed geographical information is available. Therefore, we define

¹⁰ The abbreviation is derived from the French *Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne*.

¹¹ At a more detailed NACE-level (divisions, groups, or classes), a better correspondence between NACE Rev. 1.1 and Rev. 2 could be accomplished. This information, however, is not available in the EU-LFS microdata. In addition, the Eurostat's LFS indicators only report employment counts at NUTS2 level for broad industry categories; [A-B], [C-E], [F], [G-I], [J-K] and [L-Q] at Rev. 1.1, and [A], [B-E], [F], [G-I], [J], [M-N] and [R-U] at Rev. 2.

¹² The adopted industry categories and their corresponding NACE sections are available in the Appendix (Table A3).

¹³ To the best of our knowledge, only Huber (2018) has used NUTS2 (combined with NUTS1) regions to study population elasticities to employment.

¹⁴ See also Dijkstra et al. (2019).

CZs as neighbouring travel-to-work NUTS2 regions where at least 5% of employed residents are working in the neighbouring region.¹⁵ This percentage is calculated over five years (2016-2020). As the 5%-threshold is chosen somewhat arbitrarily, we test multiple thresholds ranging from 2.5% to 10%. The latter results are reported in the robustness analyses. An overview of the CZs (depending on the adopted threshold) is available in the Appendix (Table A2). Last, alongside the estimates at NUTS2 and CZ level, we provide estimates at the NUTS1 level.

2.3. Model specification and identification

As aforementioned, we aim to investigate the population response to regional shocks in employment. Doing so, we use a panel of six quinquennial (every five-years) observations per region from 1995-2020.¹⁶ Our basic model specification takes the following general form:

$$(1) \quad \Delta \log(P_{rt}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta \log(E_{rt}) + \alpha_t + d_r + \varepsilon_{rt}$$

Where t indexes 5-year intervals and Δ represents a 5-year change, P_{rt} corresponds to the number of people in region r at time t , E denotes the number of employed people, α_t captures time fixed-effects (FE), d_r captures region FE and ε_{rt} is the error term.

Using this model, we would be able to estimate the regional migratory response of the population depending on a shift in regional employment. However, as shown by Amoir and Manning (2018), it is important to also take into account that this migratory process takes time and regional labour markets may therefore be in disequilibrium in the following period.¹⁷ Consequently, Amoir and Manning (2018) introduced an error-correction term, equal to the regional lagged log employment rate.¹⁸

$$(2) \quad \Delta \log(P_{rt}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta \log(E_{rt}) + \beta_2 \log\left(\frac{E_{rt-1}}{P_{rt-1}}\right) + \alpha_t + d_r + \varepsilon_{rt}$$

¹⁵ There are two main limitations to this approach. First, for Austria, Germany, and the Netherlands the NUTS2 classifications are unavailable in the microdata. These countries are therefore excluded from all analyses using the CZs. Second, NUTS2 area of work is not recorded if individuals work outside the country of residence. For them, we do not have information of the NUTS2 area of work. However, over five years (2016-2020) on average only 1.5% of the population in EU-27 worked outside their country of residence. Hence, we believe the impact on our results to be negligible. See also European Commission (2022).

¹⁶ For those countries who joined the EU-27 after 1995 fewer observations were used, depending on data availability.

¹⁷ For Europe, several researchers also concluded that the migratory response to a shock in employment takes several years (Pekkala & Kangasharju, 2002a, 2002b; Puhani, 2001).

¹⁸ For more information on how they derive their model, see Amoir and Manning (2018).

In the error-correction model changes in log population in region r depend on changes in log employment and the lagged log employment rate in that region, with the latter representing the extent of disequilibrium (Amior & Manning, 2018).

In addition, we recognise that the regional employment counts are endogenous, as population and employment counts are codetermined (Amior & Manning, 2018). Also, regional employment counts can be correlated with unobserved time-varying supply shocks in the error term, such as the increasing labour force participation of women in recent decades (Cipollone et al., 2014; Lechman & Kaur, 2015; Vlasblom & Schippers, 2004) and the tendency of older workers to work longer (often due to pension reforms raising the retirement age) (European Commission, 2021). Ignoring this simultaneity and potential omitted variable bias in our estimations violates the exogeneity assumption and therefore likely generates biased estimates. As suggested by Bartik (1991)¹⁹ and in line with the pivotal work of Amior and Manning (2018), we adopt an instrumental variable approach using an industry shift-share instrument (b_{rt}) to tackle the endogeneity and better isolate regional labour demand shocks.

$$(3) \quad b_{rt} = \sum_i \frac{E_{i,r,t-1}}{E_{r,t-1}} * [\log(E_{c(-r),i,t}) - \log(E_{c(-r),i,t-1})]$$

The instrument interacts regional industry (i) employment shares at $t - 1$ (given our quinquennial panel)²⁰ with the change in log industry employment in country c , excluding region r ²¹ and i containing six industry categories.²² The change in log employment is instrumented with the industry shift-share instrument and the error-correction term with the lagged industry shift-share instrument.

While this method allows us to tackle potential endogeneity issues and control for the extent of disequilibrium, this also puts a strain on our data. For each region, the first and second observation are used to construct the shift-share instrument, most often observations in 1995 and 2000. Addi-

¹⁹ Bartik's instrument was later popularised by Blanchard and Katz. (1992).

²⁰ To address concerns exogeneity of the instrument, we also estimate the population elasticity to employment using a Bartik instrument based on the regional industrial composition in 1995 (see Sensitivity and robustness analyses).

²¹ The leave-one-out approach for the growth rates is recommended by Goldsmith-Pinkham et al. (2020), to address bias resulting from finite samples. Additionally, we could use the change in log industry employment in Europe, as opposed to country c (excluding region r). This, however, largely leads to weak instrumental variable problems in our case.

²² These industry categories are based on the broad correspondence between the sections NACE Rev. 1.1 and NACE Rev. 2 (Eurostat, 2008), as well as the industry groups available in Eurostat's LFS indicators (see Appendix, Table A3).

tionally, we use the lagged shift-share to instrument the error-correction term. This implies that the estimation period runs from 2005 to 2015 in our analyses. Due to data availability (as described in the Appendix Table A1) Croatia, Denmark, Ireland, and Lithuania are dropped from our sample. One should also note that, given the leave-one-out approach for the log national industry employment (in the instrument), countries where the NUTS or CZ classification equals one region (representing the entire country) are also excluded from our analyses.²³

3. Results

3.1. Population response: benchmark analyses

In this section, we present standard linear regression and IV estimates of equation (2) at multiple regional levels, namely the NUTS2, CZ and NUTS1 level (Table 1). The simple linear regression results suggest a substantial and positive relation between regional shocks in employment and changes in population, with β_1 and β_2 estimates hovering around .5 and between .36 and .46 respectively for all three regional classification estimates. However, given that we do not control for endogeneity in these simple regressions, the coefficients cannot be given a causal interpretation.

²³ At the NUTS2 level, Cyprus, Estonia, Luxembourg, Latvia, and Malta are excluded. At the CZ level using the 5% threshold, all countries excluded at the NUTS2 level, Belgium, and Slovenia, as well as Austria, Germany, and the Netherlands (due to data availability) are excluded. At the NUTS1 level, all countries excluded at the NUTS2 level as well as Czechia, Slovenia and Slovakia are excluded.

Table 1. Population response to shocks in employment, 1995–2020

	OLS			IV		
	NUTS2 (1)	CZ (2)	NUTS1 (3)	NUTS2 (4)	CZ 5% (5)	NUTS1 (6)
Δ log emp	.498*** (.040)	.467*** (.051)	.478*** (.064)	.259*** (.048)	.263*** (.057)	.337*** (.058)
Lagged log emp rate	.458*** (.034)	.360*** (.046)	.402*** (.065)	.341*** (.054)	.289*** (.055)	.356*** (.065)
Observations	718	459	264	718	459	264
Number of regions	213	130	79	213	130	79
Countries included	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK	BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK	AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK	BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK	AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE

Note: This table reports linear regression and instrumental variable (IV) estimates across NUTS2 regions (columns 1 and 4), CZ (columns 2 and 5), NUTS1 regions (columns 3 and 6) over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the endogenous variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate, for individuals aged 15–64. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (** (*)) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

The IV estimations, which address these concerns (Table 1, Columns 4-6), predict a much lower migratory response, especially in the first five years. For the sample of NUTS2 areas the estimated initial (5-year) migration response is 0.259 in the IV specification (Column 4), close to half the estimated value in the OLS specification (0.498, Column 1). The smaller β_1 in the IV estimates as compared to the OLS estimates is what we would expect if regional population and employment growth are jointly determined and positively correlated. Shocks to regional populations through, e.g., non-work related migration, will affect aggregated regional demand and employment and lead to an overestimation of the impact of employment shocks on population in the OLS specification.²⁴ To substantiate whether our IV approach adequately tackles the concern of endogeneity, we report in Table 2 our first-stage regressions and the Cragg-Donald test statistics for testing the weakness of instruments in models with multiple endogenous variables. We find that the employment growth is solely impacted by the current Bartik instrument, and that the lagged employment rate is impacted by both the current and lagged shift-share instrument with the latter one being most

²⁴ See also Amior and Manning (2018), basic model.

strongly correlated with the error-correction term. The Cragg-Donald test statistics are well above the critical value of 7.03 (Stock & Yogo, 2005).

Table 2. First-stage regressions and Cragg-Donald test statistics: population response to shocks in employment, 1995–2020

	NUTS2 (A)	CZ (B)	NUTS1 (C)
<i>Δ log emp</i>			
Current Bartik	.688*** (.057)	.712*** (.075)	.709*** (.074)
Lagged Bartik	.014 (.040)	.000 (.046)	.054 (.042)
<i>Lagged log emp rate</i>			
Current Bartik	-.307*** (.034)	-.322*** (.044)	-.282*** (.051)
Lagged Bartik	.453*** (.039)	.473*** (.044)	.334*** (.072)
Cragg-Donald test statistic	147.855	106.366	52.991
Observations	718	459	264
Number of groups	213	130	79
Countries included	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK	BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK	AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE

Note: This table reports first-stage estimates across NUTS2 (Column A), CZ (column B), NUTS1 (Column C) regions over 1995–2020. The 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate, for individuals aged 15–64, are instrumented with the current and lagged Bartik shift-shares. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

Returning to our main IV estimates, the coefficients seem to vary little depending on the regional classification adopted. If anything, the initial (5-year) population response (the coefficient on $\Delta \log emp$) seems to be larger when studying broader regions (NUTS1 as opposed to NUTS2 or CZ). However, when we perform tests for equality in regression coefficients. These tests report the coefficients not to be statistically different from one another.²⁵ Additionally, we test whether the data constraints for each of the regional levels impact our results. To this end, we run our analysis at NUTS2 level for those countries included in the analyses at CZ and NUTS1 level, respectively. These results are reported in the Appendix, Table A4, where panel A reports the population response to shocks in employment and Panel B the first-stage regressions and the Cragg-Donald test statistics.

²⁵ Basso et al. (2019) report the population elasticity to employment to be larger at the regional (approximately NUTS1) level as opposed to the country level in the Euro Area.

While the coefficients change somewhat depending on the sample, the selection of countries does not seem to be the driving factor for the (lack of) variation in the coefficients over the three basic specifications.

Given these observations, from here on we mainly focus on the IV estimates at NUTS2 level (Table 1, Column 4). These estimates indicate that a positive (negative) shock of 10% to regional employment is linked to a 2.6% increase (decline) in population in the first five years and a 2.5%²⁶ increase (decline) in the next five years, meaning that population corrects for 51% of the shock to regional employment in ten years.

First, comparing these results to those of Amior and Manning (2018), we find the migratory response to be larger in the United States (US) where population corrects for approximately 70% (preferred model) of the shock to regional employment in the first ten years. This is in line with our expectations, as research generally indicates that in the US inter-regional migration largely corrects for regional shocks in employment, while in Europe this is (initially) mostly explained by changes in labour force participation (Decressin & Fatás, 1995). Recent literature (Beyer et al., 2015; Jauer et al., 2019), however, report both the EU and the US to have roughly equal long-run population elasticities to employment.²⁷ In addition and highly similar to our results, Beyer et al. (2015) report mobility to account for approximately 50% of the adjustment to regional employment shocks over a period of ten years.²⁸ As compared to the IV results of Huber (2018), however, we report a higher population elasticity. They find that in the EU-28 and EU-15, on average, population corrects for approximately 19% and 23% of the shock to regional employment over the period 2005-2014. However, in their model, they do not take into account that the migratory process takes time which might lead to a lower coefficient. As an additional test, we run our model excluding the error-correction term (see Appendix, Table A5). This indeed leads to lower elasticity to employment estimates.

Second, to put these numbers into perspective, we report the (unweighted) average quinquennial change to regional log employment in Table 3. We find that the average ranges from 2.1% to 3%.²⁹ However, there is large variation with Dytiki Ellada (EL63-Greece) reporting the largest negative

²⁶ This equals the remaining shock to employment of 7.4% ($= .10 \cdot .026$) after five years multiplied by the coefficient for lagged log employment rate of .341.

²⁷ The process, however, takes longer in the EU (Beyer et al., 2015).

²⁸ Their results are based on a vector autoregression model with the country-level as the unit of observation.

²⁹ Weighing the averages by the lagged regional population share does not impact our results substantially.

change of approximately 24% in 2015 and Corse (FRM0-France) reporting the largest positive change of almost 31% in 2005. In addition, 12% to almost 17% of all shocks are equal to or greater than 10% in absolute terms.

Table 3. Average (5-year) shock in employment, 1995–2020

	NUTS2	CZ	NUTS1
Mean	.026	.021	.030
Standard deviation	.068	.077	.069
Min.	-.238	-.238	-.224
Max.	.309	.309	.309
Share of shocks $\geq .1 $.121	.166	.125
Observations	718	459	264
Countries included	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK	BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK	AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE

Note: This table reports summary statistics on the 5-year change in log employment across NUTS2, CZ and NUTS1 regions over 1995-2020.

3.2. Heterogeneity in population response

While the average population elasticity is quite high, substantial differences in these elasticities within the population are present. We test the heterogeneity in responses for gender, age, country of birth (native versus foreign-born), educational level, and two subsets of countries, as well as for positive and negative shocks to regional employment. While differences among these group are often considered in the literature (Basso et al., 2019; Bound & Holzer, 2000; Faggian et al., 2007; Huber, 2018; Macisco & Pryor, 1963; Topel, 1986), it is important to stress that a strict interpretation of the estimates require strong assumptions on labour market segmentation along the lines of these groups. The analysis using subsamples based on these background characteristics inherently assume individuals are only competing for jobs within their ‘group.’ Our IV estimates (Panel A) and the associated first-stage statistics (Panel B) at the NUTS2 level are reported in Table 4. The OLS estimates at NUTS2 level, as well as all analyses (OLS and IV) at the CZ and NUTS1 level are provided in the Appendix Tables A6-A10. All variables and Bartik instruments for gender, age, country of birth and educational level use group-specific data.

First, we find that women have a higher population elasticity to employment than men. For women (men), population corrects for 76% (47%)³⁰ of the shock to regional employment in ten years. This

³⁰ Women: $.456+(1-.456)*.567=.764$; Men: $.237+(1-.237)*.303=.468$.

stronger migratory response in women is generally supported by the literature. Faggian et al. (2007) found female graduates to have a stronger migratory response than their male counterparts in the UK. They suggest this to be a partial compensation mechanism for the gender discrimination in the labour market. Older literature include Macisco and Pryor (1963) who surveyed 39 empirical studies on migration by gender and found a larger propensity to move for women.³¹

Second, we assess the heterogeneity in population response by age. Doing so, we follow Amior and Manning (2018) and adopt three age groups; 15-24, 25-44 and 45-64. Similar to them, as well as Huber (2018), we find that middle-aged individuals generally report the highest population elasticity to employment, as compared to those younger and older. For those under 25, while all quality indicators of our IV seem promising, the estimated population response however seems unlikely with young individuals leaving a region after five years following a positive shock to employment. This group of young people includes a large share of individuals still in the education system with movements possible driven by access to education opportunities. In addition, the smaller population elasticity to employment in older workers might hide older workers disproportionately dropping out of the labour force as opposed to migrating (Amior & Manning, 2018).

Third, in line with previous studies (e.g. Basso et al., 2019; Huber, 2018), we find those born outside the reporting country to be more mobile as compared to their native peers for whom we do not observe any migratory response. This mimics findings in Cadena and Kovak (2016) who finds that Mexican born immigrants to the US responded much stronger than natives following the Great Recession. The difference in elasticity to employment seems to manifest itself especially within the first five years. The estimates should, however, be interpreted with caution, especially for foreign born individuals as their counts for population and employment are often quite low.³²

Fourth, similar to Basso et al. (2019) and to the broader literature on migration by educational level (e.g. Bound & Holzer, 2000; Topel, 1986), we find higher educated individuals (beyond upper secondary education) to be more mobile. For higher (lower) educated individuals, population corrects for 84% (47%)³³ of the shock to regional employment in ten years. This difference in mobility is most often linked to migration costs, which are generally higher for less educated individuals

³¹ An exception is the study of Huber (2018), where a stronger population response among men (in the IV estimates) is reported.

³² The (unweighted) average count for population and employment in NUTS2 regions equals respectively 148 (1140) and 87 (724) for foreign-born individuals (natives).

³³ Higher educated: $.753+(1-.753)*.366=.843$; Lower educated: $.259+(1-.259)*.283=.469$.

(Bound & Holzer, 2000). Notowidigdo (2020), however, show in their recent study that the lower mobility is linked to a lower incidence of adverse labour demand shocks, rather than higher migration costs.

Fifth, we find that our main results are driven by the Western European countries. In the former (prior to the 2004 EU enlargement) EU-15 countries estimates indicate that population corrects for 43% of the shock to regional employment in the first five years and an additional 36% in the next five years.³⁴ In Eastern European countries, we remarkably do not find any significant response initially. Only after five years, a small migratory response to employment is found. While the literature typically documents the East-West migration in Europe (Barslund et al., 2014; Dobson, 2009; Dorn & Zweimüller, 2021), we are not aware of other recent estimates looking at labour market adjustment to shocks within Eastern European countries. One reason for the low response found may be the extensive East-West migration within Europe in the past two decades, the effect of which may be drowning local labour market responses.³⁵ Moreover, in line with our results, Fidrmuc (2004) found that in post-communist economies³⁶ migration plays a marginal role in correcting for shocks in employment.

Last, we test whether population responds differently depending on the sign (positive or negative) of the shock to regional employment.³⁷ While most studies assume the population response does not differ between positive and negative shocks, large differences may occur depending on e.g. the availability of jobs (during a boom or recession) (Pekkala & Kangasharju, 2002a). We, indeed, observe differences depending on the sign of the shock and find that the initial migratory response is likely higher when there is a positive shock to employment.³⁸ The coefficient is, however, only marginally significant. Notwithstanding, in the next five years, we find a much higher population elasticity to employment in regions characterised by negative (as opposed to positive) shocks to regional employment. To conclude, population seems to respond with some delay, especially when confronted with negative shocks. On the one hand, these results contradict the findings of Pekkala

³⁴ $(1-.434) \cdot .643 = .364$.

³⁵ If a relatively large share of people is moving from local labour markets in Eastern Europe to Western Europe independent on local labour market conditions due to East-West wage differentials, this may swamp any local effects that we are able to detect.

³⁶ In their paper, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, and Slovakia are studied.

³⁷ These estimates are, however, based on a limited number of observations and should therefore be interpreted with caution (especially those regarding negative shocks to employment).

³⁸ Regions characterised by a negative shock, initially have no migratory response.

and Kangasharju (2002a), as they found little difference in response depending on the shock sign. On the other hand, we similarly find migration to have a more delayed role following a negative shock (Pekkala & Kangasharju, 2002a).

Table 4. Heterogeneity in population responses to shocks in employment, IV estimates across NUTS2 regions, 1995–2020

	Gender		Age			Country of birth		Educational level		Country-groups		Shock sign	
	Female	Male	15-24	25-44	45-64	Native	Foreign-born	Higher educated	Lower educated	Western Europe	Eastern Europe	Positive shock	Negative shock
	1a	1b	2a	2b	2c	3a	3b	4a	4b	5a	5b	6a	6b
<i>Panel A. IV</i>													
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$.456*** (.100)	.237*** (.048)	-.047 (.057)	.636*** (.036)	.454*** (.045)	-.407 (.314)	.828*** (.037)	.753*** (.050)	.259*** (.043)	.434*** (.047)	.128 (.087)	.202* (.104)	.175 (.132)
Lagged log emp rate	.567*** (.131)	.303*** (.048)	-.137** (.068)	.743*** (.056)	.460*** (.080)	-.351 (.310)	.474 (.298)	.366** (.161)	.283*** (.055)	.643*** (.049)	.145** (.071)	.343*** (.055)	.869*** (.211)
<i>Panel B. First-stage</i>													
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$													
Current Bartik	.724*** (.069)	.622*** (.048)	.765*** (.071)	.731*** (.067)	.845*** (.057)	.715*** (.101)	.831*** (.081)	.758*** (.084)	.741*** (.070)	.658*** (.053)	.740*** (.113)	.390*** (.063)	.608*** (.094)
Lagged Bartik	.039 (.054)	-.005 (.039)	.103 (.064)	.049 (.058)	.088* (.049)	-.021 (.060)	.079 (.084)	.032 (.076)	.025 (.043)	.040 (.043)	.001 (.059)	.024 (.040)	.111* (.057)
Lagged log emp rate													
Current Bartik	-.512*** (.048)	-.204*** (.026)	-.646*** (.048)	-.192*** (.032)	-.254*** (.052)	-.581*** (.050)	.046 (.032)	-.125*** (.033)	-.220*** (.036)	-.352*** (.034)	-.265*** (.051)	-.408*** (.075)	-.035 (.047)
Lagged Bartik	.170*** (.044)	.594*** (.032)	.426*** (.044)	.394*** (.033)	.341*** (.062)	.229*** (.056)	.116*** (.034)	.154*** (.035)	.501*** (.036)	.370*** (.049)	.579*** (.062)	.503*** (.046)	.307*** (.052)
Cragg-Donald test statistic	22.123	157.994	59.033	125.628	54.623	10.136	10.658	18.733	122.255	73.483	38.538	39.920	38.130
Observations	718		546			445		546		521	197	476	123
Number of regions	213		154			145		154		149	64	180	57
Countries included	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK		BE BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SI SK			BE CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL IT PL PT RO SE SI SK		BE BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SI SK		AT BE DE ES BG CZ EL FI FR IT NL HU PL RO PT SE SI SK		AT BE CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL HU IT PL PT PT RO SE SK	AT BG DE EL ES FI FR RO

Note: This table reports instrumental variable (IV) estimates (Panel A) and the associated first-stage statistics (Panel B) across NUTS2 regions over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the endogenous variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate, for women aged 15–64 (Column 1a), men aged 15–64 (Column 1b), individuals aged 15-24 (Column 2a), individuals aged 25-44 (Column 2b), individuals aged 45-64 (Column 2c), individuals aged 15–64 born in the reporting country (Column 3a), foreign-born individuals aged 15–64 (Column 3b), higher educated individuals aged 15–64 (Column 4a), lower educated individuals aged 15–64 (Column 4b), individuals aged 15–64 residing in a Western European country (Column 5a), individuals aged 15–64 residing in a Eastern European country (Column 5b) and individuals confronted with a positive (Column 6a) or negative (Column 6b) shock. The 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate are instrumented with the current and lagged Bartik shift-shares. All variables and Bartik instruments for gender, age, country of birth and educational level use group-specific data. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (** (*)) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

3.3. Sensitivity and robustness analyses

We check the sensitivity and robustness of our results in several ways.³⁹ First, we weigh each observation by the lagged regional population share (Table 5, Column 1). This does not impact our results substantially. Compared to our benchmark analyses at NUTS2 level, we find that the initial response is slightly larger when correcting for population size, suggesting that population corrects for 53% (as opposed to 51%) of the shock to regional employment in 10 years.⁴⁰

Second, given the limited number of observations per region (six at max.), the (empirically demanding) region FE might burden our estimates. While Amior and Manning prefer their estimates without these controls for unobserved time-invariant supply effects, others do not estimate them at all (Bound & Holzer, 2000). We, therefore, estimate our model without FE (Table 5, column 2). We find that the estimated initial response within the first five years is slightly lower when excluding the region FE. However, while all quality indicators remain good, the relation between instruments and endogenous regressors becomes more complicated. For this reason, we prefer the specification with FE.

Third, we estimate the population elasticity to employment at the NUTS2 level using a Bartik instrument based on the regional industrial composition in 1995 (as opposed to lagged five years), to address concerns that the regional lagged industrial composition may not be sufficiently exogenous to regional supply shocks. This, unfortunately, also entails a substantial reduction in our sample size, as only six countries have (reliable) data in 1995. However, comparing our results based on the (new) instrument using the regional industrial composition in 1995 (Table 5, column 3a) to those based on the (old) moving instrument for this subset of countries (column 3b), we find the change in our instrument makes little difference, with 68% and 66%, respectively,⁴¹ of the shock to regional employment being corrected by population in ten years. Amior and Manning (2018), who use decadal changes for their shift-share instrument as well as a single historical date, link the similarity of the results to the strong persistence in regional industrial composition.

Fourth, given that the 5%-threshold for the CZs is chosen somewhat arbitrarily, we test multiple thresholds ranging from 2.5% to 10% (see Appendix, Table A2, for an overview of the CZs). We find

³⁹ Within this section, we again focus on observations at the (most detailed) NUTS2 level, unless stated differently.

⁴⁰ $.290+(1-.290)*.341$ (Table 5, Column 1).

⁴¹ $.334+(1-.334)*.525$ (Table 5, Column 3a), $.323+(1-.323)*.205$ (Table 5, Column 3b).

that the adopted threshold does not impact our results much, with the response remaining largely the same across these analyses (Table 5, Columns 4a-4c). Notwithstanding, different countries are included depending on the adopted threshold. We therefore also run these analyses for the subsample of countries included when using the smallest threshold of 2.5% (see Appendix, Table A11). Doing so, we again get similar results.

Table 5. Robustness analyses: population response to shocks in employment, 1995–2020

	Weighted IV NUTS2 (1)	Excl. FE IV NUTS2 (2)	Bartik fixed in 1995 IV NUTS2 (3a)	Moving Bartik for countries included in 3a IV NUTS2 (3b)	CZ at threshold 2.5% IV CZ 2.5% (4a)	CZ at threshold 7.5% IV CZ 7.5% (4b)	CZ at threshold 10% IV CZ 10% (4c)
<i>Panel A. IV</i>							
Δ log emp	.290*** (.046)	.199*** (.048)	.334*** (.050)	.323*** (.050)	.283*** (.063)	.269*** (.052)	.272*** (.051)
Lagged log emp rate	.341*** (.058)	.349*** (.066)	.525*** (.070)	.502*** (.069)	.299*** (.057)	.298*** (.053)	.304*** (.053)
<i>Panel B. First-stage</i>							
Δ log emp							
Current Bartik	.854*** (.067)	.724*** (.050)	.752*** (.074)	.738*** (.077)	.686*** (.083)	.735*** (.071)	.738*** (.070)
Lagged Bartik	.036 (.038)	.059* (.034)	.018 (.055)	.019 (.057)	-.007 (.049)	.007 (.044)	.009 (.043)
Lagged log emp rate							
Current Bartik	-.336*** (.038)	-.204*** (.068)	-.270*** (.040)	-.277*** (.041)	-.319*** (.048)	-.324*** (.041)	-.323*** (.041)
Lagged Bartik	.430*** (.037)	.543*** (.068)	.335*** (.052)	.352*** (.051)	.481*** (.047)	.465*** (.043)	.458*** (.042)
Cragg-Donald test statistic	252.185	26.953	65.843	76.628	83.938	127.971	135.332
Observations	718	718		368	413	500	519
Number of regions	213	213		92	117	141	147
Countries included	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK	BE EL ES FR IT SE		BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL	BE BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK	BE BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SI SK

Note: This table reports instrumental variable (IV) estimates (Panel A) and the associated first-stage statistics (Panel B) across NUTS2 regions (Columns 1 to 3b) and CZs (Columns 4a to 4c) over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the endogenous variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate for individuals aged 15–64. The 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate are instrumented with the current and lagged Bartik shift-shares. For Columns 3a and 3b the instruments are based on the regional industrial composition in 1995 (as opposed to lagged five years). Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects, unless stated differently. Robust clustered (by region or CZ) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

4. Discussion and conclusion

The ongoing technological transformations (e.g., digital transformation, artificial intelligence revolution) and the green transition towards a low-carbon society have the potential to create disruptions in the labour market. Technological advances may change demand for labour over a short period of time as well as across levels of educational attainment. This can happen even if the impact of technology is a net positive for society. Similarly, the green transition will affect workers, at least those employed in fossil extractive and related industries. To the extent that negative employment effects will be regionally concentrated - and there is some suggestive evidence of this in relation to the risk of automation (OECD, 2019) as well as for extractive industries - our results are informative about the resulting regional population dynamic of the population of working age.

In this paper, we study the persistence of regional unemployment and, more specifically, the average population response to regional labour market shocks. Doing so, we contribute to the literature in three main ways.

First, we take into account that the migratory process takes time by including both the log employment and the regional lagged log employment rate (an error-correction term) in our model, as proposed by Amior and Manning (2018). We are the first to adopt such model to the European context. Additionally, to tackle endogeneity issues in the standard linear regressions and better isolate regional labour demand shocks, we adopt an IV approach with an industry shift-share instrument.

Second, we draw on the EU-LFS microdata in the EU-27 (excluding the UK) over the period 1995-2020 for the working-age population (ages 15–64 and not in school). These data allow us to study population elasticities up to the detailed, and hardly studied, NUTS2 level.

Third, we consider travel-to-work streams, by studying the population response to labour market shocks at the level of CZs. These CZs are defined as neighbouring travel-to-work NUTS2 regions where at least 5% of employed residents are working in the neighbouring region. (In the robustness analyses, we also tested other thresholds.)

Comparing our OLS and IV estimates, we find that the OLS estimates overstate population elasticities (especially) in the first five years. Using the IV approach, we find that in ten years population

generally corrects for about 50%⁴² of a shock to regional employment at the NUTS2 and CZ level. Comparing our results to those for the US (see Amior & Manning, 2018), and in line with previous research (Decressin & Fatás, 1995), we find that the EU population elasticity is generally lower.

The overall population elasticity to employment, however, hides substantial differences in elasticities with women, individuals aged 25 to 44, foreign-born and higher educated individuals reporting higher population elasticities. These heterogeneities are generally supported by previous literature (Basso et al., 2019; Bound & Holzer, 2000; Faggian et al., 2007; Huber, 2018; Macisco & Pryor, 1963; Topel, 1986). In addition, we found our main results to be driven by Western European countries. In Eastern European countries, migration generally has a more delayed role. Also, the population response seems to differ depending on the sign of the shock to regional employment, with a negative (as opposed to a positive) shock resulting in a more delayed migratory response.

Notwithstanding, the analyses for these heterogeneous responses rely on the strong assumption that individuals only compete for jobs within the defined groups (for the background characteristics) and are subject to multiple data restrictions. Future research might focus more on these heterogeneities, especially those regarding the sign (positive or negative) of the employment shock. Additionally, within the EU-27, regional differences in the population elasticity are likely to occur, as was partly illustrated in our analyses for Western and Eastern European countries. Future research could look into other county groupings or even a comparison of all individual EU-27 countries.

⁴² At the NUTS2 (CZ) level, population on average corrects 51% (48%), 26% (26%) in the first five years and 25% (21%) in the next five years of a shock to regional employment.

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Appendix

Table A1. Data availability and aggregation of NUTS2 regions in the Eurostat microdata

	Country (Country code Alpha 2)	Data availability and region aggregation	Years included in final dataset
Countries in final dataset			
(1)	Austria (AT)	The NUTS2 classification is unavailable in the LFS microdata for AT. Eurostat's LFS statistics are used at the NUTS2 level, with data available from 1999 onwards. The NUTS1 information is available in the microdata, with data available from 1995 onwards.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(2)	Belgium (BE)	Data are available throughout the studied period (1995-2020) with consistent geographical regions.	1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(3)	Bulgaria (BG)	Data are available from 2003 onwards, due to major changes in the NUTS2 classification in 2003 for BG.	2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(4)	Czech Republic (CZ)	Data are available from 1998 onwards with consistent geographical regions. Prior to 1998, there is only one NUTS2 region in CZ.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(5)	Germany (DE)	The NUTS2 classification is unavailable in the LFS microdata for DE. Eurostat's LFS statistics are used at the NUTS2 level, with data available from 1999 onwards. The NUTS1 information is available in the microdata, with data available throughout the studied period (1995-2020).	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(6)	Greece (EL)	Data are available throughout the studied period (1995-2020) with consistent geographical regions.	1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(7)	Spain (ES)	Data are available throughout the studied period (1995-2020). Ceuta y Melilla (63) split in two regions in 1999: Ciudad de Ceuta (63) & Ciudad de Melilla (64). We aggregated these two regions into one region from 1999 onwards to have consistent geographical groups from 1995-2020.	1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(8)	Finland (FI)	Data are available from 1999 onwards, due to major changes in the NUTS2 classification in 1999 for FI. Etelä-Suomi (18) split in two regions in 2005: Helsinki-Uusimaa (1B) and Etelä-Suomi (1C). We aggregated these two regions into one region from 2005 onwards. Pohjois-Suomi (1A) and Itä-Suomi (13) became 1 large region in 2005: Pohjois-ja Itä-Suomi (1D). To have consistent geographical groups from 1995-2020, prior to 2005, we aggregated regions 1A and 13 into one region.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(9)	France (FR)	Data are available throughout the studied period (1995-2020). The boundary shift in Guadeloupe (Y1) in 2010 is ignored. This shift does not have a statistical effect, as the area concerned (Saint Barthélemy) was not covered before.	1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(10)	Hungary (HU)	Data are available from 1997 onwards. Közép-Magyarország (10) split in two regions in 2013: Budapest (11) and Pest (12). We aggregated these two regions into one region from 2013 onwards to have consistent geographical groups from 1995-2020.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(11)	Italy (IT)	Data are available throughout the studied period (1995-2020). The boundary shifts in Emilia-Romagna (H5) and Marche (I3) in 2005 are ignored.	1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(12)	Netherlands (NL)	The NUTS classifications are unavailable in the LFS microdata. Eurostat's LFS statistics are used at the NUTS2 and NUTS1 level, with data available from 1999 onwards.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(13)	Poland (PL)	Data are available from 1998 onwards. Prior to 1998, there is only one NUTS2 region in PL. Mazowieckie (12) split in two regions in 2013: Warszawski stołeczny (91) and Mazowiecki regionalny (92). We aggregated these two regions into one region from 2013 onwards to have consistent geographical groups.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020

	Country (Country code Alpha 2)	Data availability and region aggregation	Years included in final dataset
(14)	Portugal (PT)	Data are available from 1998 onwards, due to major changes in the NUTS2 classification in 1998 for PT.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(15)	Romania (RO)	Data are available from 1998 onwards. Prior to 1998, there is only one NUTS2 region in RO.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(16)	Sweden (SE)	Data are available throughout the studied period (1995-2020). The boundary shifts in Småland med öarna (21) and Västsverige (23) in 1999 are ignored.	1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(17)	Slovenia (SI)	Data are available from 2001 onwards. Prior to 2001, there is only one NUTS2 region in SI. The boundary shift in Vzhodna Slovenija (03) and Zahodna Slovenija (04) in 2010 are ignored.	2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
(18)	Slovakia (SK)	Data are available from 1998 onwards with consistent geographical regions.	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020
Countries excluded from final dataset			
(1)	Cyprus (CY)	There is only one NUTS2 region in CY. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) CY is not included in our sample.	/
(2)	Denmark (DK)	Data are available from 2007 onwards. Prior to 2007 (1991-2006), there is only one NUTS2 region in DK. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) DK is not included in our sample.	/
(3)	Estonia (EE)	There is only one NUTS2 region in EE. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) EE is not included in our sample.	/
(4)	Croatia (HR)	Data are available from 2007 onwards. Prior to 2007, there is only one NUTS2 region in HR. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) HR is not included in our sample.	/
(5)	Ireland (IE)	Data are available from 2012 onwards, due to major changes in the NUTS2 classification in 2012 for IE. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) IE is not included in our sample.	/
(6)	Lithuania (LT)	Data are available from 2013 onwards. Prior to 2013, there is only one NUTS2 region in LT. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) LT is not included in our sample.	/
(7)	Luxembourg (LU)	There is only one NUTS2 region in LU. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) LU is not included in our sample.	/
(8)	Latvia (LV)	There is only one NUTS2 region in LV. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) LV is not included in our sample.	/
(9)	Malta (MT)	There is only one NUTS2 region in MT. Due to methodological constraints (see Section 2.3) MT is not included in our sample.	/

Table A2. Commuting zones

Country code (Alpha 2)	NUTS2 regions (NUTS 2021) combined in one CZ using a threshold of ...							
	(CZ1.025)	2.5% (CS2.025) (CS3.025)		5% (CZ1.05) (CS2.05)		7.5% (CZ1.075)	10% (CZ1.10) (CZ2.10)	
BE	10, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35 (Entire country)			10, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35 (Entire country)		10, 23, 24, 31, 32, 35	10, 24, 31	32, 35
BG	31, 41							
CZ	1, 2, 4			1, 2		1, 2	1, 2	
ES	13, 21, 22, 23	30, 42		22, 23	30, 42	30, 42	30, 42	
FI	1B, 1C			1B, 1C				
FR	10, B0, C1, D2, E2	J1, L0	K1, K2	10, B0, E2		10, E2	10, E2	
HU	11, 12, 21, 22, 31, 32			11, 12, 21		11, 12		
IT	C1, C4	F1, F2, I4	H3, H4					
PL	21, 22							
PT	16, 17, 18			17, 18				
RO	31, 32			31, 32		31, 32		
SE	11, 12, 31			11, 12		11, 12	11, 12	
SI	3, 4 (Entire country)			3, 4 (Entire country)		3, 4 (Entire country)		
SK	1, 2, 3			1, 2				

Note: Commuting zones (CZs) are defined as neighbouring travel-to-work NUTS2 regions where at least 2.5%, 5%, 7.5% or 10% of employed residents are working in the neighbouring region. These percentages (thresholds) are calculated over five years (2016-2020). Note that, regardless of the CZs (as defined by each threshold), (NUTS 2021) regions 63 and 64 in ES, regions 1B and 1C in FI, regions 11 and 12 in HU, regions 91 and 92 in PL and (NUTS 2006) regions 1A and 13 in FI are aggregated into one region for all analyses to have consistent geographical groups throughout time, see Appendix A1.

Table A3. Industry classifications with (broad) correspondence between the NACE sections of Rev. 1.1 and Rev. 2

Number of industries	NACE Rev. 1.1: [section] and description	NACE Rev. 2: [section] and description
1	[A] agriculture, hunting and forestry [B] fishing	[A] agriculture, forestry, and fishing
2	industry [except construction]: [C] mining and quarrying [D] manufacturing [E] electricity, gas, and water supply	industry [except construction]: [B] mining and quarrying [C] manufacturing [D] electricity, gas, steam, and air conditioning supply [E] water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation activities
3	[F] construction	[F] construction
4	[G] wholesale and retail trade: repair of motor vehicles, motorcycles, and personal and household goods [H] hotels and restaurants [I] transport, storage, and communications	[G] wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles [I] accommodation and food service activities [H] transportation and storage [J] information and communication
5	[J] financial intermediation [K] real estate, renting and business activities	[K] financial and insurance activities [L] real estate activities [M] professional, scientific, and technical activities [N] administrative and support service activities
6	[L] public administration and defence; compulsory social security [M] education [N] health and social work [O] other community, social and personal services activities [P] activities of private households as employers and undifferentiated production activities of private households [Q] extraterritorial organisations and bodies	[O] public administration and defence; compulsory social security [P] education [Q] human health and social work activities [R] arts, entertainment, and recreation [S] other service activities [T] activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of households for own use [U] activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies

Source: Eurostat (2008, p.47)

Table A4. Population response to shocks in employment at NUTS2 level for a subsample of countries, 1995–2020

	NUTS2 – sample restricted to countries included in CZ-analyses (1)	NUTS2 – sample restricted to countries included in NUTS1-analyses (2)
<i>Panel A. IV</i>		
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$.273*** (.054)	.273*** (.049)
Lagged log emp rate	.307*** (.053)	.362*** (.055)
<i>Panel B. First-stage</i>		
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$		
Current Bartik	.721*** (.072)	.688*** (.057)
Lagged Bartik	.010 (.043)	.015 (.041)
Lagged log emp rate		
Current Bartik	-.325*** (.042)	-.309*** (.035)
Lagged Bartik	.461*** (.041)	.451*** (.039)
Cragg-Donald test statistic	123.272	140.624
Observations	498	678
Number of groups	141	199
Countries included	BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK	AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE

Note: This table reports instrumental variable (IV) estimates (Panel A) and the associated first-stage statistics (Panel B) across NUTS2 regions over 1995–2020. In Column 1 (Column 2), the sample is restricted to countries included in CZ (NUTS1) analysis in Table 1, Column 5 (Column 6). The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the endogenous variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate for individuals aged 15–64. The 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate are instrumented with the current and lagged Bartik shift-shares. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

Table A5. Population response to shocks in employment, IV estimates across NUTS2 regions, 1995–2020

	Full sample NUTS2
<i>Panel A. IV</i>	
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$.076* (.040)
<i>Panel B. First-stage</i>	
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$	
Current Bartik	.687*** (.058)
Cragg-Donald test statistic	434.250
Observations	718
Number of regions	213
Countries included	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK

Note: This table reports instrumental variable (IV) estimates (Panel A) and the associated first-stage statistics (Panel B) across NUTS2 regions over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the endogenous variable is the 5-year change in log employment for individuals aged 15–64. The 5-year change in log employment is instrumented with the current Bartik shift-shares. Throughout, we control for year effects and include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

Table A6. Heterogeneity in population responses to shocks in employment, OLS estimates across NUTS2 regions, 1995–2020

	Gender		Age			Country of birth		Educational level		Country groups		Shock sign			
	Female	Male	15-24	25-44	45-64	Native	Foreign-born	Higher educated	Lower educated	Western Europe	Eastern Europe	Positive shock	Negative shock		
Δ log emp	.448*** (.037)	.520*** (.041)	.234*** (.069)	.703*** (.026)	.535*** (.034)	.545*** (.054)	.792*** (.026)	.891*** (.023)	.466*** (.038)	.529*** (.025)	.490*** (.079)	.621*** (.041)	.250** (.095)		
Lagged log emp rate	.429*** (.035)	.433*** (.032)	.066 (.063)	.624*** (.041)	.369*** (.041)	.492*** (.054)	1.093*** (.131)	.768*** (.069)	.362*** (.035)	.654*** (.029)	.301*** (.060)	.486*** (.036)	.485*** (.128)		
Observations	718	718	546	546	546	445		546	546	521	197	476	123		
Number of regions	213	213	154	154	154	145		154	154	149	64	180	57		
Countries included	AT BE BG CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SI SK		BE BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SI SK			BE CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SI SK		BE BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SI SK		AT BE DE ES FI FR IT NL PT SE		BG CZ EL HU PL RO SI SK		AT BE CZ DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE SK	

Note: This table reports linear regression estimates across NUTS2 regions over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the independent (endogenous) variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate, for individuals aged 15–64. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

Table A7. Heterogeneity in population responses to shocks in employment, OLS estimates across CZs, 1995–2020

	Gender		Age			Country of birth		Educational level		Country groups		Shock sign	
	Female	Male	15-24	25-44	45-64	Native	Foreign-born	Higher educated	Lower educated	Western Europe	Eastern Europe	Positive shock	Negative shock
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$.409*** (.048)	.503*** (.050)	.245*** (.073)	.690*** (.029)	.537*** (.037)	.565*** (.057)	.787*** (.031)	.890*** (.027)	.468*** (.044)	.460*** (.034)	.493*** (.080)	.619*** (.054)	.257** (.101)
Lagged log emp rate	.355*** (.045)	.341*** (.042)	.067 (.066)	.606*** (.041)	.365*** (.042)	.499*** (.052)	1.106*** (.138)	.752*** (.072)	.358*** (.037)	.570*** (.034)	.292*** (.059)	.405*** (.053)	.486*** (.137)
Observations	459		459			364		459		278	181	277	108
Number of regions	130		130			122		130		72	58	108	50
Countries included	BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK		BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK			CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK		BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK		ES FI FR IT PT SE	BG CZ EL HU PL RO SK	CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK	BG EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO

Note: This table reports linear regression estimates across CZs over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the independent (endogenous) variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate, for individuals aged 15–64. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

Table A8. Heterogeneity in population responses to shocks in employment, OLS estimates across NUTS1 regions, 1995–2020

	Gender		Age			Country of birth		Educational level		Country groups		Shock sign	
	Female	Male	15-24	25-44	45-64	Native	Foreign-born	Higher educated	Lower educated	Western Europe	Eastern Europe	Positive shock	Negative shock
Δ log emp	.492*** (.048)	.483*** (.066)	.371*** (.059)	.723*** (.037)	.562*** (.045)	.562*** (.074)	.790*** (.032)	.947*** (.027)	.489*** (.048)	.457*** (.042)	.550*** (.121)	.515*** (.053)	.372** (.169)
Lagged log emp rate	.412*** (.044)	.364*** (.066)	.137* (.072)	.605*** (.060)	.410*** (.071)	.491*** (.059)	.915*** (.105)	.788*** (.111)	.365*** (.043)	.541*** (.034)	.311*** (.092)	.435*** (.067)	.613*** (.180)
Observations	264		252			188		252		200	64	174	47
Number of regions	79		75			57		75		59	20	66	22
Countries included	AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT NL PL PT RO SE		AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE			AT BE EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE		AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE		AT BE DE ES FI FR IT NL PT SE	BG EL HU PL RO	AT BE BG DE EL FI HU IT NL PL PT RO SE	BG DE EL ES FR IT PL PT RO

Note: This table reports linear regression estimates across NUTS1 regions over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the independent (endogenous) variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate, for individuals aged 15–64. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

Table A9. Heterogeneity in population responses to shocks in employment, IV estimates across CZs, 1995–2020

	Gender		Age			Country of birth		Educational level		Country groups		Shock sign	
	Female	Male	15-24	25-44	45-64	Native	Foreign-born	Higher educated	Lower educated	Western Europe	Eastern Europe	Positive shock	Negative shock
	1a	1b	2a	2b	2c	3a	3b	4a	4b	5a	5b	6a	6b
<i>Panel A. IV</i>													
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$.439*** (.096)	.240*** (.059)	-.062 (.062)	.601*** (.045)	.429*** (.050)	-.527 (.482)	.873*** (.062)	.745*** (.060)	.236*** (.049)	.383*** (.066)	.131 (.089)	.336*** (.110)	.154 (.144)
Lagged log emp rate	.504*** (.125)	.234*** (.050)	-.149** (.072)	.693*** (.056)	.449*** (.082)	-.438 (.451)	.287 (.442)	.385** (.158)	.269*** (.060)	.609*** (.091)	.138* (.071)	.294*** (.051)	.914*** (.241)
<i>Panel B. First-stage</i>													
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$													
Current Bartik	.754*** (.093)	.679*** (.066)	.767*** (.077)	.676*** (.081)	.853*** (.061)	.689*** (.115)	.756*** (.094)	.731*** (.096)	.711*** (.076)	.680*** (.074)	.743*** (.117)	.414*** (.085)	.673*** (.104)
Lagged Bartik	.019 (.062)	-.018 (.045)	.099 (.068)	.044 (.062)	.087* (.052)	-.056 (.067)	.090 (.096)	-.001 (.081)	.020 (.046)	.012 (.054)	.010 (.061)	.011 (.042)	.144** (.064)
Lagged log emp rate													
Current Bartik	-.565*** (.063)	-.228*** (.035)	-.685*** (.053)	-.169*** (.038)	-.245*** (.057)	-.589*** (.055)	.050 (.038)	-.130*** (.039)	-.223*** (.038)	-.263*** (.050)	-.271*** (.052)	-.484*** (.108)	-.014 (.054)
Lagged Bartik	.204*** (.049)	.629*** (.037)	.427*** (.047)	.409*** (.036)	.371*** (.067)	.248*** (.065)	.109*** (.038)	.168*** (.038)	.521*** (.040)	.281*** (.063)	.591*** (.064)	.547*** (.051)	.311*** (.058)
Cragg-Donald test statistic	20.141	104.375	44.716	79.257	51.300	6.025	6.511	16.341	89.179	23.968	35.327	24.740	32.017
Observations	459		459			364		459		278		108	
Number of regions	130		130			122		130		72		50	
Countries included	BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK		BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK			CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK		BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK		ES FI FR IT PT SE BG CZ EL HU PL RO SK		CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK BG EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO	

Note: This table reports instrumental variable (IV) estimates (Panel A) and the associated first-stage statistics (Panel B) across CZs over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the endogenous variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate, for women aged 15–64 (column 1a), men aged 15–64 (column 1b), individuals aged 15–24 (column 2a), individuals aged 25–44 (column 2b), individuals aged 45–64 (column 2c), individuals aged 15–64 born in the reporting country (column 3a), foreign-born individuals aged 15–64 (column 3b), higher educated individuals aged 15–64 (column 4a), lower educated individuals aged 15–64 (column 4b), individuals aged 15–64 residing in a Western European country (column 5a), individuals aged 15–64 residing in an Eastern European country (column 5b) and individuals confronted with a positive (column 6a) or negative (column 6b) shock. The 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate are instrumented with the current and lagged Bartik shift-shares. All variables and Bartik instruments for gender, age, country of birth and educational level use group-specific data. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by CZ) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) (10%) significance level.

Table A10. Heterogeneity in population responses to shocks in employment, IV estimates across NUTS1 regions, 1995–2020

	Gender		Age			Country of birth		Educational level		Country groups		Shock sign	
	Female	Male	15-24	25-44	45-64	Native	Foreign-born	Higher educated	Lower educated	Western Europe	Eastern Europe	Positive shock	Negative shock
	1a	1b	2a	2b	2c	3a	3b	4a	4b	5a	5b	6a	6b
<i>Panel A. IV</i>													
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$.446*** (.088)	.308*** (.058)	-.038 (.070)	.656*** (.042)	.448*** (.055)	-.058 (.229)	23.060 (4018.82)	.866*** (.143)	.309*** (.054)	.433*** (.053)	.227 (.136)	.364*** (.068)	.215* (.104)
Lagged log emp rate	.456*** (.116)	.336*** (.063)	-.071 (.123)	.803*** (.077)	.415*** (.096)	-.059 (.241)	-101.454 (18444.2)	-.936 (4.592)	.199** (.078)	.471*** (.071)	.250* (.123)	.328*** (.073)	.936** (.336)
<i>Panel B. First-stage</i>													
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$													
Current Bartik	.663*** (.092)	.676*** (.078)	.602*** (.112)	.697*** (.078)	.801*** (.057)	.645*** (.124)	.451* (.240)	.792*** (.107)	.712*** (.099)	.661*** (.082)	.794*** (.154)	.485*** (.116)	.691*** (.156)
Lagged Bartik	.101* (.057)	.042 (.041)	.225* (.116)	.108** (.053)	.084 (.056)	.069 (.069)	.276 (.189)	-.109 (.122)	.022 (.044)	.068 (.059)	.053 (.052)	.064 (.042)	.162** (.078)
Lagged log emp rate													
Current Bartik	-.449*** (.074)	-.174*** (.056)	-.581*** (.085)	-.145*** (.042)	-.209*** (.064)	-.430*** (.082)	.098 (.081)	-.016 (.036)	-.200*** (.042)	-.249*** (.059)	-.392*** (.097)	-.396*** (.137)	-.061 (.064)
Lagged Bartik	.102 (.065)	.450*** (.085)	.316*** (.079)	.305*** (.050)	.203** (.079)	.205** (.089)	.061 (.070)	.017 (.041)	.359*** (.070)	.260*** (.075)	.315** (.153)	.366*** (.107)	.242*** (.056)
Cragg-Donald test statistic	9.090	71.639	16.337	44.723	16.410	7.997	0.000	0.167	52.394	18.442	9.949	33.515	13.365
Observations	264		252			188		252		200		174	
Number of regions	79		75			57		75		59		66	
Countries included	AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE		AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE			AT BE EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE		AT BE BG DE EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE		AT BE DE BG EL HU PL RO		AT BE BG DE EL FI HU IT NL PL PT RO SE	

Note: This table reports instrumental variable (IV) estimates (Panel A) and the associated first-stage statistics (Panel B) across NUTS1 regions over 1995–2020. The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the endogenous variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate, for women aged 15–64 (column 1a), men aged 15–64 (column 1b), individuals aged 15–24 (column 2a), individuals aged 25–44 (column 2b), individuals aged 45–64 (column 2c), individuals aged 15–64 in the reporting country (column 3a), foreign-born individuals aged 15–64 (column 3b), higher educated individuals aged 15–64 (column 4a), lower educated individuals aged 15–64 (column 4b), individuals aged 15–64 residing in a Western European country (column 5a), individuals aged 15–64 residing in an Eastern European country (column 5b) and individuals confronted with a positive (column 6a) or negative (column 6b) shock. The 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate are instrumented with the current and lagged Bartik shift-shares. All variables and Bartik instruments for gender, age, country of birth and educational level use group specific data. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) (10%) significance level.

Table A11. Robustness analyses: population response to shocks in employment across commuting zones, 1995–2020

	IV CZ 2.5% (repetition of Table 5)	IV CZ 5% restricted to countries included in CZ 2.5%	IV CZ 7.5% restricted to countries included in CZ 2.5%	IV CZ 10% restricted to countries included in CZ 2.5%
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
<i>Panel A. IV</i>				
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$.283*** (.063)	.263*** (.057)	.266*** (.056)	.267*** (.055)
Lagged log emp rate	.299*** (.057)	.289*** (.055)	.297*** (.054)	.301*** (.054)
<i>Panel B. First-stage</i>				
$\Delta \log \text{ emp}$				
Current Bartik	.686*** (.083)	.712*** (.075)	.719*** (.074)	.718*** (.074)
Lagged Bartik	-.007 (.049)	.000 (.046)	.004 (.045)	.005 (.044)
<i>Lagged log emp rate</i>				
Current Bartik	-.319*** (.048)	-.322*** (.044)	-.322*** (.043)	-.323*** (.043)
Lagged Bartik	.481*** (.047)	.473*** (.044)	.469*** (.043)	.464*** (.042)
Cragg-Donald test statistic	83.938	106.366	114.131	116.453
Observations	413	459	476	483
Number of regions	117	130	135	137
Countries included	BG CZ EL ES FI FR HU IT PL PT RO SE SK			

Note: This table reports instrumental variable (IV) estimates (Panel A) and the associated first-stage statistics (Panel B) across CZs over 1995–2020. In column 2 to 4, the sample is restricted to countries included in CZs based on a 2.5% threshold (Column 1). The dependent variable is the 5-year change in log population, and the endogenous variables are the 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate for individuals aged 15–64. The 5-year change in log employment and the lagged (5-year) log employment rate are instrumented with the current and lagged Bartik shift-shares. Throughout, we control for year effects. All regressions include region fixed effects. Robust clustered (by region) standard errors are reported between parentheses. *** (**) (*) indicates significance at the 1% (5%) ((10%)) significance level.

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